

RULES OF COMPOSITES DESIGN: A REVIEW

STEPHEN W. TSAI
Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics
Stanford University
Stanford, California 94305-4035 USA

ABSTRACT

Design of composite materials and structures have often been practices as an art of "black aluminum." Many design rules are made intuitively from the experience of metallic structures. Regardless of origin, rules should be challenged to avoid either unconservative or cost ineffective design. To gain credibility, all rules deserve to be validated by classical laminated plate theory together with quadratic failure criteria. Many rules turn out to be simple and easy to apply. They can lead to reliable and competitive design of composite structures.

Keywords: Laminate design, sizing, design rules, laminate ranking

1. INTRODUCTION

Design of materials and structures are often more art than science. Experience is a good teacher when the time-consuming learning process is available. For modern composite materials which has a history less than 30 years, experience has been limited in aerospace applications. Since aluminum has been used as the base-line material, intuition and design judgment have been strongly influenced by the aluminum experience.

The heat-and-beat, build-and-break, and cut-and-try are more readily achieved with metals than composite materials. Fundamental differences between aluminum and composite materials arise from:

- Homogeneity versus heterogeneity and lamination
- Isotropy versus macroscopic anisotropy
- Ductility versus linear and brittle behavior
- Fracture versus progressive, ply-by-ply failures, and
- Differences in corrosion and fatigue resistance

For composite materials, mathematical models provide critical information to guide design. In the last 30 years, much effort in mathematical models has been made, and are helping our technology to have good designers. As a minimum, an integrated micro- and macromechanics

analysis model can provide rationally derived rules of design. In this talk, we hope to show how rules of design can be generated to reinforce and refute intuitively derived rules. The goal is intended to establish rules rationally, and make them easy to apply.

2. RULE OF MIXTURES

First of all, rules are intended to simplify designs. They reduce the scope of design, and focus on critical issues. Good rules lead to safe and cost-effective design. The most famous rule of composite materials is the rule of mixtures. It states that a composite property is a linear function of the volume fractions of the constituents. There are two rules: the parallel and series connected constituents. For unidirectional composite ply, the parallel rule applies to: density, and longitudinal stiffness, strength, Poisson's ratio and expansions. The series rule applies to: transverse and shear moduli. To be more predictive, the latter rule needs to be modified, for example, by use of stress-partitioning parameter. With these rules, a useful micromechanics framework can be built to model not only the stiffness and strength of a unidirectional ply but also to effects of temperature and moisture, and the role of the fiber/matrix interface. If there is no micromechanics framework, it is nearly impossible to establish quantitatively the contribution of the constituents, and the interface. Empirical approach alone is not adequate.

We believe that quantitative description is important in both absolute and relative terms. It is not enough to say that an interface is good or bad. We need to know how many Pascals represent a good interfacial strength. We also do not understand what is a fiber or matrix dominated behavior. These are examples of vaguely defined experiments and behavior. With a framework of micromechanics, we may be able to clarify observations with quantitative precision.

3. OTHER RULES

Other simple rules of composites design include the outlawing of unbalanced laminates. First of all, it is a misconception that unbalanced laminates warp. Unsymmetric laminates do. In addition unbalanced is not a proper description of a laminate. A laminate can be thin or thick, symmetric or unsymmetric, or light or heavy. These characteristics are scalar; i.e., independent of the coordinate system. But we cannot say that a laminate is balanced or unbalanced, stiff or compliant, strong or weak, conductive or resistant without the reference to a specific coordinate system. These characteristics are not scalar. The difference in these scalar and non-scalar characteristics is the same as that between composite laminates and black aluminum.

Strain to failure is more meaningful than stress to failure. In fact, it is a common rule in industry to define design limit using a normal strain component; say, 0.4 percent strain. Treating strain as a scalar is again the same as treating laminates as black aluminum. Strains deserve 3 components. Paying attention of one component only does not provide sufficient information. To do it right, strain invariants or, better still, failure invariants are simple and analytically correct as a basis of strength.

Another rule is the 10-percent rule. This may be viewed as an extension of the use of balanced laminates. Each ply orientation within a laminate must be at least 10 percent of the total. If there are four ply angles, for example, 0, 90, 45 and -45 degrees, 40 percent made up by 10 percent each of the four angles of the laminates are committed in each laminate. Any directionality of the laminate must be derived from selecting the ply angles from the remaining 60 percent. If six ply angles are permitted, we have only 40 percent of plies that can be utilized for directionality if the 10 percent rule is applied. It is reasoned that the 10 percent rule provides a good insurance against unanticipated and/or secondary load. We think that this rule is arbitrary. We can show by laminated plate theory the optimum number of ply angles and secondary load can be systematically defined. The 10 percent rule, like that of balanced

laminates, penalizes composite materials. We need rules that would lead to safe and cost-effective design. We cannot afford rules that may impose penalties or lead to unsafe designs.

It is our intent to examine not only existing rules but also new ones with the intent of making composite materials safe, reliable, damage tolerant and cost-effective. Composite materials may be black, but they certainly are not aluminum. We can make progress if we believe in analytic models.

4. LAMRANK

The ranking of strength in families of laminates is one of the simplest methods to determine the optimum laminates for multiple load conditions. Using laminated plate theory and quadratic failure criteria for plies with and without micro cracks, it is straightforward to determine the following for any number of loading conditions:

- Optimum number of ply angles from two to eight
- Optimum ratios of ply angles in each sub-laminate having two to ten plies
- Controlling load condition
- Relative performance of laminates to the quasi-isotropic $[\pi/4]$ laminate

Intuitively obvious rules generated by LamRank are:

- If a single load is uniaxial tensile, $[0]$ is the best
- If a single load is pure shear, $[\pm 45]$ is the best

Other rules are not intuitively obvious include:

- If a single load is biaxial tensile, $[0/90]$ is the best for only certain ratios of tensile stresses and are also dependent on materials
- If a single load is uniaxial compression, $[0]$ may not be the best; bi- and tri-axial laminates are the best and are also dependent on materials

In general, it is safe to say that optimum ply angles depend on the load conditions and materials. Universal rules are not easily defined. There are no obvious requirements for using more than three ply angles. If 4-angle laminates are used, there must be additional justification beyond the optimum static strength; for example, easy fabrication. But fewer angle may mean lower cost and have fewer ply failure modes.

Balanced laminates are found to be optimum if applied stress is bi-axial: normal components only. This is not unexpected. When shear stress is present, unbalanced laminates would be optimum unless the shear is fully reversible.

If a laminate is designed to take fully reversible flexural stress, the best laminates can also be selected. If the flexural or shear stress is not fully reversible, there is no obvious rule. We recommend this problem be solved by using multiple load conditions in LamRank.

5. SUB-LAMINATE RULES

The number of plies in sub-laminates should be kept as low as possible. Lower ply numbers lead to lower cost in manufacturing, fewer ply drops and tougher laminates than higher ply numbers. There is need to exceed 10-ply sub-laminates. Lower ply numbers also allow easier selection of the optimum ply angles.

Rules governing ply grouping can also be guided by the total number of plies required. We recommend homogenized laminates, which are defined by those having the same in-plane and flexural stiffnesses. Homogenized laminates are resistant to delamination. Thus the lower the ply number in the sub-laminate, the higher the repeating index, and higher the toughness. Instead of having a rule of ply grouping never higher than 3 by some US companies, we recommend a rule based on the degree of homogenization.

It is easy to show that sub-laminates that are repeated 10 times would lead to a homogenized laminate within a error of less than 5 percent. For symmetric laminates, the total repeated sub-laminates would be 20. If we have a 160-ply symmetric laminate, a ply grouping up to 8-ply sub-laminate would be permissible. Thus the grouping is a function of the total ply number, not an absolute number of 3. When we have an 8-ply sub-laminate the permissible ply group within a sub-laminate may be as high as 7 in a $[0_7/90]$ sub-laminate. When we follow this rule faithfully, a $[0/90]$ laminate must have 40 plies or more to achieve the desired homogenization. This requirement may not be met for many practical laminates. The toughness may then be compromised. But for laminates having hundreds of plies, this rule is helpful in maximizing ply grouping in a sub-laminate without compromising the laminate toughness. Thinner plies than the standard 0.125 mm unit ply thickness can enhance laminate toughness for thin laminates. This concept has been applied to the design of a golf shaft.

Ply drops can also be rationalized by the rule on homogenization. Thus each structure should be no more than ten ply drops, and ply drops are not made ply by ply, but sub-laminate by sub-laminate. Each ply drop entails a number of fixed cost of templates, "eyebrows" and associated labor of debalking. The goal is to minimize, not maximize, the number of ply drops. We do not believe that we should limit the ply drop on a ply by ply basis.

Spiral stacking within each sub-laminate is another guideline to improve laminate toughness. For $[\pi/4]$ laminates, $[0]$ and $[90]$ are interspersed by $[45]$ or $[-45]$. Then $[\pi/3]$ is better than $[\pi/4]$ because tri-directional sub-laminates are automatically spirally stacked. Additional attention is not required.

6. BEST PANELS

The selection of the optimum panels depends, among many considerations, the boundary conditions. From the standpoint of bending, buckling and vibration, angle-ply and cross-ply laminates are preferred over $[\pi/4]$ laminates. We are unable to state simple rules for all panels of different materials, ply orientations and boundary conditions. Our advice would be to use a fast, easy to use finite element analysis and to start the design with as few ply angles and ply number in the sub-laminate as possible. We do know that for high aspect ratio plates (highly elongated plates), unidirectional composites are better than laminates.

Panel tapering to reduce weight can also be determined analytically. Several common panels have been determined. Using the same sub-laminate but different number of repeats would simplify the determination of the locations of sub-laminate drop. Again, we have found that uni-, bi- and tri-directional laminates are more efficient than quadri-directional ones.

Symmetric laminates have been found to be stiffer than unsymmetric laminates. The bending/twisting coupling leads to more compliant panels. This may be a useful rule if a more compliant construction is desired.

There are many ways to increase the flexural stiffness of a panel. One is the use of sandwich core. The stiffness increase in terms of weight is well known. The skins carries all the loads, while the core provides the shear rigidity. Another way to increase flexural stiffness of a panel is by stiffeners. There are many forms of stiffener geometry, size, and spacing. The cost of processing stiffened panels is higher than sandwich construction. One possible solution to offset the higher cost is to use a grid reinforcement, such as the ortho and isogrid. The grid can be designed to have the desired balance between bending and twisting similar to a laminate design to have the desired in-plane Young's and shear moduli. The grid members are all [0] which would provide the highest stiffness possible.

7 A SIZING STRATEGY BY LAMRANK

One unique feature of composite materials that is fundamentally different from isotropic materials is the design for multiple load conditions. For isotropic materials, the controlling load among multiple loads is easily determined based on the largest normal or shear components. Shear strength is approximately one half of the tensile or compressive strength. But for composite materials, the controlling load among multiple loads depends on the particular laminate. LamRank, for example, evaluates the strength of each laminate under each load. The strongest laminates are then ranked in accordance with their ability to withstand all the anticipated multiple loads.

LamRank can be extended as a basis for sizing a composite structure subjected to multiple loading conditions. Recognizing the loads can be functions of space and time. At each time, a structure may be subjected to loads that vary from location to location. At each location in the structure, the load would vary with time as the operating conditions change. Because the time- and space-dependency of the loading conditions, a structure is subjected to hundreds if not thousands of loads. It is a rather complex problem of design, but with simplifying assumptions LamRank can be used to select the best laminates for the structure.

First, we will limit the design loads to finite number of locations and do not consider local stress concentrations for the initial attempt for the global sizing. Secondly, we will consider one laminate for the entire structure, and use tapering to adjust local load conditions. We will recommend that tapering be done in units of sub-laminates. The key to the identification of optimum laminates and the corresponding controlling loads lies the use of LamRank. Recent study has shown that of all possible loads that a structure can see at different times and at different locations there are no more than eight vertices that define the rectangular box that encloses all the load vectors in the plane-stress space. This rectangular box is the most conservative outer boundary of all the anticipated loads. More precise outer boundary can be developed to further tighten the basis of the optimum laminate selection. The important point is that of all seeming unlimited number of loads, only eight loads are needed as inputs to LamRank which would rapidly determine the top ranking laminates for these loads, which would be of sufficient strengths for all loads.

This strategy that leads to the best laminate for the entire structure is easy to do, and can lead to tapering as load changes from location to location. The magnitude of the loads would determine the number of repeated sub-laminates since the same sub-laminate is used throughout the entire structure.

With this strategy, the resulting structure can be sized without the burden of the 10-percent rule, limit strains, and unbalanced laminates. It is not unreasonable to expect that a structure that is

sized by rationally derived rules will most likely be **competitive in structural performance and cost-effectiveness.**

8. CONCLUSIONS

Design rules are useful to simplify design. They must be derived experience and models. Rules by edict are not recommended. Many rules should be challenged to ensure that composite structures are not unduly penalized. LamRank is a useful tool. Other rules which remain undeveloped include the optimum layups for bending, hybridization and out-of-plane reinforcement. If a laminate is homogenized, the optimum laminate for flexure will be the same for in-plane having fully reversible stress resultants. Rules governing micromechanical variables are also not well defined. It is hoped that as analysis tools emerge design rules will soon follow.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author wish to acknowledge the help from his colleagues and students at Stanford University. Mr. Francois-Jacques Cordonnier's work in the generalization of LamRank is particularly appreciated.